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Role of Vegetable Farming in Enhancing Household Income and Livelihood Conditions in Pacharia Village, Kamrup District, Assam

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Abstract

Objectives: This study examines the role of vegetable farming in enhancing household income and livelihood conditions in Pacharia village of Kamrup district, Assam, with an emphasis on income generation, livelihood diversification, and socio-economic improvement within a floodplain agricultural environment. **Methods:** The study is based on primary data collected from 86 households through stratified random sampling supplemented by secondary data from government sources. Quantitative tools, including correlation analysis, mean, median, and standard deviation, and the Gini coefficient, were applied alongside qualitative methods to analyse socio-economic conditions, landholding structure, income distribution, and livelihood strategies. **Findings:** The findings show that 67.72% of the population is of working age, indicating a substantial agricultural labour force. Vegetable farming is an important source of livelihood, with an average annual household income of ₹283,985. However, 36.05% of households reported annual incomes below ₹200,000, reflecting persistent income disparities. A statistically significant positive relationship was observed between education and income ($r = 0.66$, $p < 0.001$, 95% CI: 0.52-0.76), with average household income increasing from ₹169,554 among illiterate respondents to ₹867,655 among postgraduates. Fragmented landholdings (average: 0.34 hectares), inadequate infrastructure, and market-related constraints continue to limit productivity and income stability. **Novelty:** The study provides a micro-level assessment that links socio-economic conditions, income distribution, and production constraints in a floodplain agricultural setting. The findings indicate that the transition towards commercially oriented vegetable farming remains gradual and uneven due to resource and institutional limitations. **Implications:** The study highlights the need for improved storage infrastructure, stronger market linkages, enhanced access to institutional credit, and climate-resilient agricultural practices to improve the sustainability of vegetable-based livelihoods.

Keywords: Vegetable farming; household income; livelihood conditions; income distribution; floodplain agriculture; Kamrup district

1 Introduction

Agriculture plays a central role in supporting rural economies in developing countries, where a large proportion of the population depends on smallholder farming systems for employment and income generation⁽¹⁾. In many rural regions, agriculture remains the primary source of livelihood due to limited non-farm employment opportunities^{(2), (3)}. Recent studies indicate that agricultural diversification through high-value crops, particularly vegetable cultivation, has emerged as an important strategy for strengthening rural income, employment opportunities, and socio-economic resilience among smallholder households^{(4), (5), (6)}.

In recent years, vegetable farming has gained prominence due to its relatively high economic returns, shorter production cycles, and expanding market demand⁽⁷⁾. Commercial vegetable cultivation has contributed to income increases, employment generation, and improved livelihoods, particularly among small and marginal farming households and women farmers^{(4), (8)}. In addition to its economic significance, vegetable cultivation contributes to improved diets and rural economic development^{(9), (10)}.

In India, agriculture continues to employ a substantial proportion of the rural workforce, with increasing policy emphasis on high-value agriculture to improve farmers' incomes and reduce vulnerability to market and environmental risks⁽¹¹⁾. However, smallholder farmers frequently encounter structural constraints such as fragmented landholdings, inadequate infrastructure, limited market access, and limited institutional support, which hinder agricultural productivity and profitability⁽¹²⁾. Recent research further suggests that climate variability and environmental stressors are intensifying livelihood uncertainties, particularly in climatically fragile regions such as floodplains⁽¹³⁾.

Assam, located in the Brahmaputra valley, represents a unique agro-ecological region characterised by fertile alluvial soils and high agricultural potential, but also recurrent flooding and environmental instability⁽¹³⁾. Within this region, Kamrup district has emerged as an important centre of vegetable production, due to its proximity to urban markets and favourable climatic conditions. The district benefits from its proximity to Guwahati, one of the major urban markets in Northeast India, thereby enhancing market accessibility and commercial opportunities for vegetable growers. In recent years, improved road connectivity, expanding peri-urban demand, and increasing participation of small and marginal farmers in commercial vegetable cultivation have contributed to the growing significance of vegetable farming in the district. Pacharia village, located within this dynamic agricultural landscape, represents a typical floodplain farming environment in which vegetable cultivation plays an important role in shaping household incomes and livelihood conditions. However, despite favourable agro-climatic conditions and market potential, farmers continue to face challenges related to fragmented landholdings, infrastructural limitations, input accessibility, and market fluctuations. Therefore, the selection of Pacharia village provides an appropriate setting for examining the role of vegetable farming in enhancing rural livelihoods within the broader socio-economic context of Kamrup district.

A review of recent literature indicates that although several studies have highlighted the positive contributions of vegetable farming to rural income, employment, and improved livelihoods, most have examined these dimensions separately rather than through an integrated household-level framework. For instance, Manickam et al.⁽⁴⁾ focused primarily on crop diversification and labour returns, while Mukaila et al.⁽⁷⁾ focused primarily on the income and employment effects of vegetable farming. Similarly, Thapa and Pant⁽⁸⁾ analysed gender participation and household income, whereas Kalita⁽¹³⁾ examined infrastructural and marketing constraints in Assam agriculture. Studies by Bhandari and Paudel⁽⁵⁾ and Vasishta⁽⁶⁾ assessed livelihood improvement and livelihood capitals, respectively, but with limited socio-economic depth and smaller sample coverage. Consequently, interrelationships among income distribution, landholding structure, expenditure behaviour, livelihood disparities, and production constraints remain insufficiently explored within a single analytical framework, particularly in floodplain agricultural environments where environmental conditions significantly influence rural livelihoods.

To provide a systematic comparison of previous studies and to identify the existing research gaps, the major literature relevant to vegetable farming and livelihoods is summarised in Table 1.

In this context, the present study examines the role of vegetable farming in enhancing household income and livelihood conditions in Pacharia village of Kamrup district, Assam. Unlike many earlier studies that primarily focused on isolated aspects of vegetable cultivation, the present study adopts an integrated analytical framework to examine income generation, employment, landholding structure, educational attainment, expenditure behaviour, and livelihood disparities in a single empirical investigation. Through a micro-analysis conducted in a floodplain agricultural setting, the study contributes to a broader understanding of vegetable farming as a rural livelihood strategy and offers useful insights for sustainable agriculture and rural development in Assam.

Table 1. Comparative Literature Summary of Studies on Vegetable Farming and Livelihood

Reference	Focus of study	Methodology	Key Contributions	Identified Limitations	Gap Addressed by the Present Study
(3)	Indigenous vegetables & livelihood (Nigeria)	Survey (400 HH), Principal Component Analysis, Propensity score Matching	29.4% higher income; improved livelihood	Region-specific focus	Provides an integrated livelihood framework in Assam
(4)	Vegetable diversification (East India)	Field experiments	Improves income, labour returns, and women's empowerment	Limited socio-economic depth	Provides detailed livelihood and income analysis
(5)	Vegetable farming & livelihood (Nepal)	Survey (45 HH), Correlation test	Improved livelihoods	Small sample; limited scope	Expands to a larger sample and multi-dimensional analysis
(6)	Livelihood capitals (Nepal)	Survey (72 HH) using convenience and snowball sampling, chi-square test	81.9% depend on vegetable income; improved assets	Non-probability sampling; limited scope	Uses systematic sampling and a broader framework
(7)	Vegetable farming & livelihood (Nigeria)	Survey (400 HH), regression	Positive impact on income, employment; 89.4% women's participation	Limited analysis of utilisation & sustainability	Examines income distribution, utilisation, and constraints
(8)	Gender roles in commercial vegetable farming and household income (Nepal)	Purposive sampling	Joint gender participation enhances income through vegetable farming, but unequal decision-making power	limited scope with a lack of broader livelihood analysis	Provides integrated analysis of gender, income, market, land and environmental factors
(10)	Role of vegetable farming in rural livelihoods and support systems	Mixed-method (survey, interviews, and focused group discussion)	Improves income, food security, and livelihood diversification; highlights the role of community-based organisations	Limited focus on environmental challenges and region-specific production analysis	Addresses floodplain-specific challenges, production and productivity in Kamrup
(13)	Agricultural challenges (Assam)	Descriptive study	Identifies infrastructure & market issues	No empirical micro-level data	Provides village-level quantitative analysis
Present Study	Vegetable farming & livelihoods (Pacharia, Assam)	Mixed-method (86 HH; statistical and qualitative analysis)	Income ₹283,985; diversification 56.98%; employment, gender role, constraints (market, climate, land)	Micro-level scope	Integrates an empirical framework linking socio-economic, economic and environmental dimensions in the floodplain context

2 Methodology

2.1 Profile of the study area

The present study was conducted in Pacharia village of Sualkuchi Development Block, Kamrup District, Assam (Figure 1). It is situated in the northern floodplain of the Brahmaputra River. The village is confined within 26° 13' 19" N to 26° 15' 13" N latitude and 91° 37' 19" E to 91° 38' 16" E longitude. It is located approximately 15 km from Guwahati city. The village covers an area of 3.4 square kilometres with a population of 1,943 persons (as per the 2011 Census). The population density is 570 persons per square kilometre. The village has 430 households, with a literacy rate of 79.34%. The presence of various caste groups, including Brahmins, Kshatriyas, Vaishyas, and Shudras, characterises the village's demographic structure. Of the total

population, 53.37% is male, and 46.63% is female. The child population (below 6 years) constitutes 7.7 per cent of the total population. The average sex ratio is 874 females per 1000 males.

Fig 1. Location of the study area

2.2 Sources of data

This study uses both primary and secondary data. Primary data were collected from 86 households in Pacharia village, Kamrup district, Assam (March–June 2024) using a stratified random sampling method to ensure representation across socio-economic and agricultural categories. The households were stratified primarily by landholding size and participation in vegetable farming activities. From the total 430 households in Pacharia village, 20% of the households (86 households) were selected proportionately from different strata through random sampling for detailed field investigation.

The sample size was determined using Yamane’s (1967) formula for a finite population at a 95% confidence level and a permissible error margin of 10%:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n denotes the sample size, N represents the total number of households, and e indicates the permissible sampling error.

The dataset includes key socio-economic and agricultural parameters such as educational attainment, annual household income, landholding size, cropping pattern, and employment generation. Secondary data were obtained from official sources, including the Directorate of Census Operations and Government of Assam reports⁽¹⁴⁾.

2.3 Data Analysis and Tools

Data were processed through coding, cleaning, and validation to ensure consistency and reproducibility. Quantitative analysis was carried out using standard statistical techniques, including mean, median, standard deviation, Pearson’s correlation coefficient, and Gini coefficient. Median income was used to measure the central tendency of household income distribution and to minimise the influence of extreme income values within the sample.

The relationship between educational attainment and annual household income was analysed using Pearson's correlation coefficient, defined as:

$$r = \frac{\sum(x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y - \bar{y})^2}}$$

where r represents the Pearson correlation coefficient, x denotes the educational attainment of the respondents, y denotes the annual household income, and \bar{x} and \bar{y} represents their respective mean values.

Landholding variability was measured using standard deviation:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum f(x - \bar{x})^2}{N}}$$

Where σ represents the standard deviation, f is the frequency of households in different landholding categories, and x represents landholding size, \bar{x} indicates the mean landholding size, and N represents the total number of households.

Income inequality among vegetable farming households was assessed using the Gini coefficient derived from grouped income distribution data and class midpoints:

$$G = 1 - \sum(X_i - X_{i-1})(Y_i + Y_{i-1})$$

Where X represents the cumulative proportion of households and Y represents the cumulative proportion of income.

The statistical significance of correlation analysis was evaluated using p -values and 95% confidence intervals. The major problems faced by vegetable farmers were identified through a combination of structured questionnaire surveys, open-ended household interviews, field observations, and focused discussions with respondents during the survey (Appendix B). Frequently reported issues were classified and summarised into thematic categories for analysis and interpretation. Reliability and validity of the collected data were ensured through a pilot survey, standardised questionnaires, field verification, and data triangulation.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Socio-economic profile and livelihood structure

The socio-economic characteristics of vegetable farming households in Pacharia significantly influence household income, livelihood conditions, and agricultural practices. The findings reveal that 67.72% of the population is of working age (14-60 years), indicating a relatively strong labour force in the village (Appendix Table 1). The remaining 32.28% constitute dependent population groups, reflecting a moderate dependency burden on economically active members. The gender composition comprises 53.4% males and 46.6% females, indicating substantial participation of both men and women in agricultural activities. Women, in particular, contribute significantly to labour-intensive farming operations such as transplanting, harvesting, sorting and marketing. Previous studies have similarly found that women's participation in agriculture contributes positively to productivity and household welfare, particularly within smallholder farming systems⁽⁸⁾.

Household size also exerts an important influence on livelihood organisation and labour availability. More than 52% of households consist of 5-6 members, indicating the predominance of medium-sized families in the study area (Appendix Table 2). Such household structures are advantageous for vegetable cultivation, which is generally labour-intensive and dependent on family-based agricultural labour. Similar findings have been reported in rural livelihood studies, which suggests that medium-sized households possess greater flexibility in labour allocation and income diversification strategies⁽¹⁵⁾.

The educational profile of the respondents indicates a moderate level of literacy, with 89.53% of the population being literate, although participation in higher education remains limited (Appendix Table 3). Gender disparities in literacy are still evident, particularly at higher education levels. Earlier studies have also reported that educational inequalities continue to constrain technological adoption and agricultural innovation in rural India⁽¹⁶⁾. Nevertheless, farmers in the study area continue to rely substantially on indigenous knowledge and traditional farming practices, which remain important for local agricultural adaptation and sustainability, as noted in recent agroecological research⁽¹⁷⁾. Overall, these socio-economic characteristics significantly influence labour availability, income-generating capacity, and livelihood conditions of vegetable-farming households in the study area.

3.2 Economic condition, income distribution and landholding structure

Vegetable farming constitutes a major source of livelihood for rural households and contributes significantly to household income generation in the study area. However, the economic base of farming households remains relatively constrained by the predominance of small and fragmented landholdings. More than half of the surveyed households (58.14%) possessed less than 0.24 ha of land, indicating the dominance of marginal farmers in the village (Appendix Table 4). Only 9.30% of the households owned more than 0.96 ha of land, reflecting limited access to larger cultivable areas. The mean landholding size is 0.34 ha, while the median landholding size is 0.24 ha, suggesting that the majority of households possessed land below the average size. Furthermore, the standard deviation of 0.29 ha indicates moderate variation in land distribution among households. The prevalence of fragmented and small landholdings limits mechanisation, economies of scale, irrigation expansion, and market-oriented production, thereby constraining agricultural productivity and income generation. Similar trends of land fragmentation and marginal farming have been widely reported in rural India and are considered major structural challenges affecting agricultural sustainability and livelihood security⁽¹⁸⁾.

The mean annual household income of the respondents is ₹283,985, whereas the median annual income is ₹304,350, indicating moderate income variation among households. Approximately 36.05% of the households earned less than ₹200,000 annually (Appendix Table 5), suggesting the persistence of low-income conditions among a substantial section of vegetable farming households. The relatively high standard deviation (₹204,510) further indicates considerable disparity in household earnings. In addition, the Gini coefficient of 0.352 indicates moderate income inequality in the study area. These findings suggest that although vegetable farming contributes positively to livelihood improvement and income generation, the economic benefits are unevenly distributed across households due to differences in landholding size, production scale, market access, and farming experience. Similar observations have been reported in recent studies, which emphasise that the economic outcomes of agricultural diversification are often uneven and context-specific⁽¹¹⁾.

3.3 Relationship between Educational Attainment and Income

A correlational study was undertaken to analyse the association between educational attainment and household income to move beyond descriptive socio-economic variables and to examine the causes of livelihood outcomes. The association between educational status and household income among vegetable farmers in Pacharia village demonstrates a positive correlation between educational attainment and annual household income. The Pearson correlation coefficient ($r = 0.66$, $p < 0.001$, 95% CI: 0.52-0.76) indicates a statistically significant moderate-to-strong positive relationship between education and income (Appendix Table 6). Households with higher levels of education reported higher annual incomes, with average household income increasing from ₹169,554 among literate respondents to ₹867,665 among post-graduate respondents. However, the relationship was not strictly linear, as households with higher Secondary education recorded a slightly lower average income (₹418,033) than HSLC-qualified households (₹472,519). This variation is attributed to differences in farming experience, occupational diversification, engagement in non-farm employment, and the scale of vegetable cultivation among respondents. The overall findings suggest that educational attainment plays a significant role in enhancing income opportunities, improving farm management practices, and facilitating better market participation among vegetable farming households.

This positive connection is consistent with recent empirical findings that education improves farmers' productivity, market engagement and income diversification. Research has shown that education level is a strong driver of agricultural revenue through better decision-making, the adoption of advanced technology, and the effective allocation of resources⁽¹⁹⁾. Similarly, knowledge-based competencies, such as digital literacy and access to information, are important for improving economic outcomes for rural households⁽²⁰⁾.

However, the correlation is substantial but not absolute, which means income also depends on other complementary characteristics such as landholding size, access to irrigation, availability of financing and market linkages. Recent research in agricultural economics demonstrates that household income variability is determined by a combination of human capital and structural factors in farming systems⁽²¹⁾. Education is thus important for improving livelihood outcomes, but for sustainable income growth among vegetable farmers, a multidimensional approach that considers both human and physical capital would be required.

3.4 Utilisation of vegetable income

The utilisation pattern of vegetable income reflects a subsistence-oriented livelihood strategy. All households (100%) prioritise consumption, followed by operating costs (72.09%), indicating immediate survival and farm maintenance needs (Appendix Table 7). Low savings (38.37%) and high debt repayment (48.84%) indicate financial weakness, while capital investment (53.49%) and diversification (56.98%) show partial commercialisation. Recent research on smallholder financial behaviour

reveals similar trends, indicating that insufficient savings and substantial debt hinder long-term investment⁽²²⁾. The current analysis, however, reveals low investment in marketing (27.91%), indicating weak integration into value chains, in contrast to findings from more developed agricultural regions. This adds to the evidence that even in high-value agricultural systems, micro-level financial behaviour is largely subsistence-driven, especially in environmentally sensitive areas.

3.5 Constraints in Vegetable Farming

Vegetable farming in Pacharia village is constrained by a combination of market, infrastructural, environmental, and institutional challenges that adversely affect productivity, profitability, and livelihood stability (Appendix Table 8). Farmers frequently reported market price fluctuations, inadequate storage facilities, and weak transportation networks as major constraints, resulting in unstable returns and significant post-harvest losses. Such challenges are common in commercial vegetable production systems where inadequate market integration increases farmers' dependence on intermediaries and reduces profitability^{(7), (23)}.

At the production level, limited access to quality seeds, fertilisers, and pesticides, along with rising input and labour costs, restrict farmers' capacity to improve productivity and adopt modern technologies⁽²⁴⁾. Financial constraints further limit investment in irrigation, mechanisation, and improved cultivation practices, particularly among marginal farming households. Environmental pressures such as erratic rainfall, water scarcity, land degradation, and climate variability also continue to affect vegetable cultivation in the floodplain environment of Assam⁽¹³⁾. In addition, pest and disease infestations remain major concerns due to inadequate technical knowledge and limited access to extension support services⁽²⁴⁾.

Institutional limitations further intensify these challenges. Farmers reported inadequate training opportunities, limited awareness of sustainable farming practices, and insufficient institutional and policy support. These interconnected constraints collectively reduce income stability and weaken farmers' ability to reinvest in agricultural activities.

3.6 Prospects of Vegetable Farming

Vegetable farming in Pacharia village offers considerable scope for rural economic advancement, given the productive floodplain environment and the growing commercial importance of vegetables in the regional agricultural economy. The gradual shift towards market-oriented cultivation has created opportunities for crop diversification, seasonal employment, and supplementary income generation among farming households. Emerging practices such as organic farming, local value addition, and improved participation in marketing may offer opportunities to strengthen the sustainability and profitability of vegetable farming in the study area^{(25), (26)}.

However, the extent of these benefits varies across households because of differences in landholding size, production capacity, and access to agricultural resources. The findings suggest that greater technological accessibility, stronger farmer networks, and improved institutional coordination would play an important role in expanding the long-term viability of vegetable-based livelihoods in the floodplain areas of Kamrup district.

4 Conclusion

The present study provides a micro-level assessment of the role of vegetable farming in shaping household income and livelihood conditions in Pacharia village of Kamrup district, Assam. The findings reveal that vegetable cultivation constitutes an important component of the rural economy, supported by a relatively strong working-age population (67.72%). The sector contributes substantially to household livelihoods, with an average annual household income of ₹283,985, and also serves as a primary and supplementary source of income for farming households. Furthermore, 56.98% of households were engaged in diversified income-generating activities, indicating a gradual transition towards semi-commercial agricultural practices.

However, the study also highlights significant socio-economic and structural constraints that affect the sustainability of vegetable-based livelihoods. Household income distribution remains uneven, with 36% of households earning below ₹200,000 annually. Financial vulnerability is further reflected in the high proportion of indebted households (48.84%) and the relatively low household savings (38.37%). In addition, fragmented landholdings, with an average farm size of 0.34 ha, along with post-harvest losses and market-related challenges, continue to limit productivity and profitability. The findings, therefore, indicate that the transition from subsistence-oriented cultivation to commercially viable vegetable farming in the floodplain environment remains gradual and uneven, shaped by multiple structural and socio-economic constraints.

4.1 Policy Implementations and Recommendations

4.1.1. *Infrastructural Development*

The study identified poor storage facilities, transportation difficulties, and post-harvest losses as major constraints affecting vegetable farming households. Therefore, strengthening rural infrastructure by establishing cold storage facilities, grading units, rural collection centres, and improved transportation networks would help reduce post-harvest losses and improve farmers' market returns. Improved infrastructure would also facilitate better market integration and minimise distress sales among small and marginal farmers.

4.1.2. *Market Strengthening*

Since more than 58% of households possess less than 0.24 ha of land, promoting Farmer-Producer Organisations (FPOs) and cooperative marketing systems would particularly benefit marginal and small vegetable growers by enhancing collective bargaining power, improving access to larger markets, and reducing dependence on intermediaries. Organised market systems can reduce the need for middlemen, ensure fair prices, and help farmers become more involved in value chains.

4.1.3. *Financial Inclusion*

The findings revealed considerable income disparities among households, with 36.05% earning less than ₹200,000 annually. Expanding access to institutional credit, crop insurance, and financial support mechanisms would reduce dependence on informal borrowing and enable lower-income farmers to invest in improved inputs, irrigation facilities, and modern cultivation practices.

4.1.4. *Capacity Building and Skill Development*

Farmers frequently reported problems related to climate variability, pest infestation, limited technical knowledge, and rising production costs. Therefore, strengthening agricultural extension services and providing training in climate-resilient farming practices, integrated pest management, scientific nutrient management, and sustainable cultivation techniques would improve productivity and livelihood resilience among vegetable-farming households.

4.1.5. *Gender Empowerment*

The participation of both men and women in vegetable cultivation highlights the importance of gender-inclusive agricultural development. Enhancing women's access to training, institutional participation, financial services, and agricultural decision-making processes could improve household welfare and livelihood security.

4.1.6. *Institutional and Policy Support*

The study indicates that sustainable vegetable farming requires coordinated institutional support, including market reforms, financial assistance, extension services and effective implementation of agricultural development programmes. Strengthening collaboration among government agencies, local institutions, and farmer organisations would enhance policy outreach and support long-term agricultural sustainability in floodplain farming areas.

4.2 Future Prospects and Research Directions

Vegetable farming in Pacharia village demonstrates considerable potential to improve household income and livelihood conditions through diversification, value addition, and improved market participation. However, future progress will depend on strengthening adaptive farming practices, improving access to technology, and enhancing institutional coordination within floodplain agricultural systems. Future research should focus on longitudinal changes in household income, livelihood resilience, climate adaptation strategies, gender dimensions of agricultural transformation, and the role of digital marketing and supply chain innovations in expanding rural economic opportunities. Comparative studies across different floodplain regions of Assam may further contribute to understanding the sustainability and long-term viability of vegetable-based livelihood systems.

4.3 Limitations of the study

The current study is subject to certain limitations. The study was confined to a single village in Kamrup district, which may limit the applicability of the findings to other places. The study used a cross-sectional design, based on primary survey data collected during a specific period. Household income data were self-reported and may be subject to memory bias or estimation errors. Additionally, the absence of a comparative control village restricts broader comparative interpretation of the findings. The study

also relied in part on Census 2011 data for village-level demographic information, as more recent disaggregated census records were unavailable; these were supplemented by field surveys and local administrative records collected in 2024.

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6 Contributory Statement

Saraswati Bhattarai conducted the research and wrote the original manuscript. Prof. Abani Kumar Bhagabati critically revised the work, supervised the research process, and approved the final version for publication. Both authors have read and approved the final manuscript.

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Appendix A

Table 1. Age-sex composition of the vegetable farming households

Age (Years)	Male	Percentage	Female	Percentage	Total	Percentage
Below 6	8	1.94	20	4.85	28	6.79
6-14	21	5.1	36	8.74	57	13.84
14-60	166	40.29	113	27.43	279	67.72
Above 60	25	6.07	23	5.58	48	11.65
Total	220	53.4	192	46.6	412	100

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 2. Family size of the vegetable farming households

No. of a family member	No. of households	Percentage
4	9	10.47
5	24	27.91
6	21	24.42
7	14	16.28
8	10	11.63
9	3	3.49
10	2	2.33
11	3	3.49
Total	86	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 3. Educational attainment of the vegetable farming households

Educational Qualification	Male		Female		Total	
	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage	No.	Percentage
Illiterate	3	5.08	6	22.22	9	10.47
Primary	11	18.64	5	18.52	16	18.60
Upper Primary	9	15.25	4	14.81	13	15.12
Under HSLC	12	20.34	2	7.41	14	16.28
HSLC	10	16.95	5	18.52	15	17.44
Higher Secondary	9	15.25	3	11.11	12	13.95
Under Graduate	4	6.78	1	3.70	5	5.81
Post Graduate	1	1.69	1	3.70	2	2.33
Total	59		27		86	100.00

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4. Size of land holdings of vegetable farming households

Size of land (ha)	Category	No. of households	Percentage of households (%)	Cumulative percentage (%)	Mean Landholding size (ha)	Median Landholding size (ha)	Standard Deviation (ha)
Less than 0.12	Marginal	24	27.91	27.91	0.34	0.24	0.29
0.12-0.24	Marginal	26	30.23	58.14			
0.24-0.48	Small	18	20.93	79.07			
0.48-0.96	Small-Medium	10	11.63	90.70			
More than 0.96	Medium	8	9.30	100.00			
Total	-	86	100.00	-			

Note: Landholding categories were grouped into smaller operational classes to capture variations among predominantly marginal and small-scale vegetable-farming households in the study area. Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 5. Economic condition and income distribution of vegetable farming households

Income (in ₹'000)	No. of households	Percentage	Mean Income (₹)	Median Income (₹)	Standard Deviation (₹)	Gini Coefficient
Below 200	31	36.05	283,985	304,350	204,510	0.352
200-400	23	26.74				
400-600	25	29.07				
600-800	4	4.65				
Above 800	3	3.49				
Total	86	100.00				

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 6. Relationship between educational attainment and annual household income of vegetable farming households

Level of Education	Average Annual Income (₹)	No. of households	Percentage of households	Mean Annual Income (₹)	Standard Deviation (₹)	Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value	95% Confidence Interval (CI)
Illiterate	169,554	9	10.5	283,985	204,510	0.66	<0.001	0.52-0.76
Primary	208,974	16	18.6					
Upper Primary	278,688	13	15.1					
Under HSLC	289,706	14	16.3					
HSLC	472,519	15	17.4					
Higher Secondary	418,033	12	14.0					
Graduate	650,188	5	5.8					
Post Graduate	867,665	2	2.3					

Source: Calculated by the researcher from the data based on the field survey, 2024

Table 7. Utilisation of vegetable income by the vegetable farming households

Domain of Use	No. of household	Percentage
Household Expenses	86	100
Operational Expenses	62	72.09
Capital Investment	46	53.49
Debt Repayments	42	48.84
Savings and reserves	33	38.37
Diversification	49	56.98
Marketing and Sales	24	27.91
Community Contribution	22	25.58

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 8. Problems of vegetable farming in Pacharia Village

Problem	Description
Market Fluctuations	Unstable prices due to demand-supply imbalances lead to income instability.
Poor Infrastructure	Lack of proper storage and transportation facilities causes post-harvest losses.
Limited Access to Quality Inputs	Difficulty in obtaining high-quality seeds, fertilisers, and pesticides.
Impact of Climate Change	Erratic rainfall, rising temperatures, and extreme weather events affect yields.
Pest and Disease Infestation	Increased vulnerability to pests and diseases due to inadequate pest control measures.
Financial Constraints	Limited access to credit and financial resources prevents investment in better farming practices.
Lack of Market Linkages	Farmers face challenges connecting with larger markets, leading to dependence on local traders.
High Production Cost	The rising costs of labour, fertilisers, and other inputs reduce profitability.
Land Degradation	Overuse of chemical fertilisers and pesticides leads to soil fertility decline.
Water Scarcity	Limited access to irrigation facilities affects crop yield and productivity.
Lack of Training and Awareness	Farmers often lack knowledge of modern farming techniques and sustainable practices.
Government Policy Gaps	Inadequate agricultural policies fail to provide the necessary support.
Post-Harvest Losses	Poor handling and lack of cold storage facilities lead to significant wastage.

Source: Field survey, 2024

Appendix B

Household Survey Schedule cum Questionnaire

Study Title: Role of Vegetable Farming in Enhancing Household Income and Livelihood Conditions in Pacharia Village, Kamrup District, Assam.

The information collected through this survey is intended solely for academic research purposes and will be kept confidential.

General Information

1. Questionnaire No.: _____
2. Name of Investigator: _____
3. Date: _____
4. Village/Ward: _____

Section A: Socio-economic Profile

5. Name of the respondent: _____
6. Gender: Male Female
7. Age: _____ years
8. Educational Qualification:
 Illiterate Primary Upper Primary HSLC Higher Secondary Graduate Post Graduate
9. Family Size: _____ members

10. Main Occupation:

- Vegetable Farming Agriculture Wage Labour Business Service Others _____

11. Secondary source of Income (if any)

- Livestock
 Wage Labour
 Business
 Fishery
 Service
 None
 others _____

12. Type of Family: Nuclear Joint

Section B: Agricultural Landholding details

13. Total Landholding: _____ bigha/hectare

14. Area under Vegetable Cultivation: _____ bigha/hectare

15. Major Vegetables Grown: _____

16. Source of Irrigation:

- Rain-fed Tube Well River/Pond Pump Set

17. Type of Seeds Used:

- Local HYV/Hybrid

18. Have you received agricultural training?

- Yes No

19. Who mainly participates in vegetable farming activities?

- Male members
 Female members
 Both jointly

Section C: Income and Livelihood

20. Annual Household Income:

- Below ₹200,000
 ₹200,00–400,000
 ₹400,00–600,000
 ₹600,00–800,000
 Above ₹800,000

21. Approximate Annual Income from Vegetable Farming: ₹ _____

22. Has vegetable farming improved your livelihood? Yes No

23. Areas of Improvement (tick applicable):

- Income
 Housing
 Education
 Health Care
 Savings
 Social Status

24. How is vegetable income mainly utilised?
- Household Expenses
 - Farming Investment
 - Debt Repayment
 - Savings
 - Children's Education
 - Health Care
25. Does your household currently have savings?
- Yes No
26. Is your household currently in debt/loan?
- Yes No
27. Major Source of Loan:
- Bank
 - Cooperative
 - Moneylender
 - Relatives/ Friends
 - Self-help Group
28. Employment generated from vegetable farming:
- Self-employment
 - Family labour
 - Hired labour

Section D: Problems in Vegetable Farming

29. Major problems faced (tick applicable):

Problems	Tick
Market fluctuations	<input type="checkbox"/>
Poor storage facilities	<input type="checkbox"/>
High production cost	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pest and disease attack	<input type="checkbox"/>
Water scarcity	<input type="checkbox"/>
Climate change impacts	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of quality inputs	<input type="checkbox"/>
Financial constraints	<input type="checkbox"/>
Poor transportation	<input type="checkbox"/>
Lack of training	<input type="checkbox"/>

30. Do you experience post-harvest losses?
- Yes No
31. Main reason for post-harvest losses:
- Lack of storage
 - Transportation delay
 - Market price fall
 - Pest/ Damage
 - Others _____

32. Where do you mainly sell vegetables?
- Local Market
 - Wholesale Market
 - Through Middlemen
 - Direct to Consumers
33. Most serious problem: _____

Section E: Future Prospects and Suggestions

34. Do you think vegetable farming has good future prospects?
- Yes No
35. What support is most needed?
- Cold Storage
 - Irrigation
 - Credit Facilities
 - Training
 - Better Market Access
 - Government Subsidy
 - Farmer Producer Organisation (FPO)
36. Suggestions for improvement: _____

Date:
Place:

Signature of the Investigator